

1 **Tree Based Machine Learning and Global Models for Long-term Rainfall Estimation:**
 2 **Intercomparison and Evaluation over Bahir Dar, Ethiopia**

3 **Getnet Yirga¹, U. Jaya Prakash Raju¹, Assaye Gedifaw², Ayanew Nigusie³**

4 ¹Department of Physics, Washera Geospace and Radar Science Laboratory, Bahir Dar
 5 University, Bahir Dar, P. O. Box. 79, Ethiopia.

6 ²Department of Physics, Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia

7 ³Department of Physics, Oda Bultum University, Ethiopia

8 Corresponding author address: getnetyirga41@gmail.com

9 **Graphical Abstract**

10

11 **Abstract**

12 Rainfall plays a crucial role in atmospheric, agricultural, meteorological, and hydrological
 13 processes. This study aims to provide an efficient and accurate model by comparing tree-based
 14 machine learning (ML) approach and global numerical weather prediction model; ECMWF for
 15 predicting long term rainfall. Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGB) and Regression Tree (RT)
 16 tree-based machine learning algorithms are utilized in this study and compared with global model.
 17 Local metrological parameters (relative humidity, dew point temperature, minimum temperature,
 18 maximum temperature, wind speed, convective available potential energy, and sunshine) and
 19 large-scale climate variable (sea surface temperature) were used as input during model
 20 development. Initially database was preprocessed and then partitioned into a training set and a
 21 testing set. The GridsearchCV technique was used for tuning the parameters of the models. **LGB**
 22 **exhibits strong performance with the highest coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.991$ for daily and**
 23 **0.996 for monthly), lowest root mean squared error (RMSE = 1.14 mm for daily and 0.383 mm**
 24 **for monthly), lowest mean squared error (MSE = 1.992 for daily and 0.146 for monthly), and**
 25 **lowest mean absolute error (MAE = 0.899 mm for daily and 0.302 mm for monthly).** For both

26 temporal variations, the LGB model show significantly higher accuracy than both RT and
27 ECMWF. Relative humidity is the most influential meteorological parameter for rainfall
28 **estimation** identified by the random forest (RF) feature important with value of 0.4129. Rainfall is
29 strongly correlated with dew point temperature (Tdew), minimum temperature (Tmin) with the
30 value of 0.94 and 0.91 respectively using heat-map analysis. An agricultural decision support
31 system that is still in development will incorporate the suggested models in Ethiopia. The study
32 will be a priceless resource for those who are planning and managing water resources in the future
33 in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia.

34 **Keywords: Bahir Dar Climate, ECMWF, LGB, Meteorological Variables, RT**

35 **1. Introduction**

36 These days, problems related to climate change and global warming are worldwide concerns. One
37 important aspect of weather change is rainfall, which is the most important meteorological
38 parameter throughout Africa. This is due to the fact that rain-fed agriculture makes up the majority
39 of the continent's economy and that rainfall has a high impact on crop production in many places.
40 Unusually high or low rainfall can cause floods or droughts, respectively, with catastrophic effects
41 on the environment and human welfare (Diro et al., 2008). In many areas of the continent, the
42 current gauge network is unable to give timely or sufficient information regarding the pattern of
43 rainfall because of unequal distribution, missing data, and sparse observations. This leads to the
44 use of global numerical models like ECMWF (Dinku et al., 2007; Diro et al., 2009; Koutsouris et
45 al., 2016; Olaniyan et al., 2018). It was found that they are performed less well in terms of capturing
46 the observed long-term trends and unable to predict extreme rainfall phenomena in many regions
47 of African sector (Koutsouris et al., 2016; Lemma et al., 2019; Olaniyan et al., 2018). Additionally,
48 local biases are present in ECMWF model and tend to estimate rainfall in the Ethiopia (Diro et al.,
49 2009; Gleixner et al., 2020). These studies highlighted the short comings of this global model in
50 African region. Several neural networks based have been developed in African region to fill this
51 gap (Abebe & Endalie, 2023; Endalie et al., 2022; Ojo & Ogunjo, 2022). The results of these
52 investigations revealed that, in comparison to global models, NN-based models show great
53 promise in capturing the overall dynamics of rainfall changes. In contrast to other machine learning
54 methods, this does not mean that NN models always produce accurate **estimation** in each scenario.
55 Because NN algorithms require a lot of data to fully utilize their potential, they often overfit small
56 datasets (Piotrowski & Napiorkowski, 2013).

57 In recent years, future weather **estimation** like rainfall will heavily rely on tree based machine
58 learning techniques (Kumar et al., 2023). They are appropriate for problems that are too complex
59 or large for global model approaches. Recently, numerous technological and scientific sectors,
60 including atmospheric weather research, have shown great interest in machine learning techniques
61 (Geetha & Nasira, 2014) with a focus on modeling the nonlinear relations, like rainfall. In response
62 of technology advancement and birth of light gradient boosting (Ke et al., 2017; Microsoft, 2016)
63 (LGB; hereafter) and regression tree model (Breiman, 2017) (RT; hereafter) and dynamics of
64 rainfall scenario, atmospheric science community models and predicts rainfall using this machine
65 learning techniques beyond NN models and the global model around the world and African sector.
66 For example, study by (Appiah-Badu et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2022; Misra et al., 2021; Monego et
67 al., 2022; Ridwan et al., 2021; Yirga, 2023; Zhou et al., 2021) modeled rainfall using machine
68 learning approaches. The findings have demonstrated that machine learning techniques are
69 efficient in modeling rainfall, even in both large and small amount of data. Additionally, tree-based

70 algorithms are not expensive because they don't necessitate a significant number of computational
71 resources and training time compared to NN algorithms(Bentéjac et al., 2021; Ramsundram et al.,
72 2016). As a result, machine learning algorithms are relatively simple to optimize compared to NN
73 techniques.

74 In previous studies conducted in the African region, machine learning methodologies other than
75 tree-based algorithms were primarily used for modeling rainfall focus on short-term data, using
76 small scale and local metrological input parameters. Even study by (Endalie et al., 2022) in
77 Ethiopia on modeling rainfall with limited input parameters and ignoring large-scale climate
78 indices and stressed the importance of global climatic indices like sea surface temperature on their
79 motivation. Due to the focus on short-term rainfall **estimation**, the smaller number of local
80 metrological parameters, insufficient studies with large-scale climate indices, the lower accuracy
81 of models, motivates us to look for an alternative method for modeling rainfall variability using
82 large scale climate indices like sea surface temperature (SST) and local metrological indices
83 including Convective available potential energy (CAPE) as input parameter. Due to the hotness of
84 the issue and reviewing the previous works: not enough research has been done on evaluating
85 different machine learning models for long-term rainfall **estimation**. **It has also been observed that**
86 **no studies have compared tree-based machine learning and global models for rainfall estimation.**
87 **This gap has motivated the current research, which aims to explore the development of a new**
88 **feasible model using local input meteorological parameters and large-scale climatic indices for**
89 **rainfall estimation and modeling.**

90 Consequently, this study has been conducted to test the effectiveness of tree-based algorithms
91 models rainfall using LGB and RT models and compares with the existing global numerical
92 weather prediction model called European Center for Medium Weather Forecast (ECMWF;
93 hereafter) to identify the reliable model for accurate rainfall prediction.

94 **2. Materials and Methods**

95 **2.1. Study Area and Data**

96 Our study area focuses on Bahir Dar sector where its neighbor with Lake Tana Basin, the largest
97 lake in Ethiopia (Figure 1). Its geographical location is 11.57 latitude and 37.36 longitudes. Bahir
98 Dar City is one of the largest and most rapidly expanding cities in Ethiopia. It is the political,
99 economic, and cultural center of Amhara National Regional State (ANRS), the second-most
100 populous region in the country. In addition, the city is one of the major tourist centers in the country
101 because of its cultural heritage (such as the Lake Tana Monasteries and religious festivals) and
102 natural attractions (such as the Blue Nile Falls, birds, and hippos). The area is also characterized
103 by rich biodiversity and recognized as a Biosphere Reserve by UNESCO. According to data from
104 the Central Statistics Agency (Ethiopia, 2013) in 2017, about 350,000 people live in the city.

105

106 **Figure 1: The study area.**

107 In Bahir Dar, the agricultural sector can be characterized as segmented, highly dependent on
 108 rainfall, and lacking permanent watercourses. This is also true of horticulture, agro-industrial
 109 processing, urban agriculture, manufacturing, and a variety of service businesses. On the other
 110 hand, the main economic activity in the Bahir Dar is tourism, which attracts large numbers of
 111 population. Furthermore, the diverse range of meteorological conditions in Bahir Dar render
 112 rainfall **estimation** a crucial matter. When combined with its temporal estimation, it forms a crucial
 113 component for making informed decisions and mitigating potential hazards associated with abrupt
 114 spikes and the notable dispersion of the impacted region.

115 **Daily local meteorological data was collected from the Bahir Dar metrological institute, located in**
 116 **Bahir Dar (latitude: 11.610 N, Longitude: 37.380 E, altitude 1800m), between the years 1993 and**
 117 **2022.** The collected metrological parameters include maximum temperature (Tmax), minimum
 118 temperature (Tmin); Relative humidity (RH), wind speed (Wspeed), sunshine (Sunshine), dew
 119 point temperature (Tdew) and rainfall (R). Other local metrological parameter, Convective
 120 Available Potential Energy (CAPE) and one of large-scale climate indices Sea Surface
 121 Temperature (SST), hourly data sets from the years 1993 to 2022, from European Centre for
 122 Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF) fifth generation reanalysis ERA-5. It provides hourly
 123 data with a 0.25° spatial resolution with hourly intervals and is easy to access via Copernicus'
 124 Climate Data Store with ([https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-
 125 singlelevels?tab=form](https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-singlelevels?tab=form)). The hourly Data sets are converted in to daily format using panda-python
 126 programing software. The summary meteorological data and large-scale climate variables are
 127 described in Table 1.

128 Table 1. Description of data in the study.

Parameters	Symbol used in study	Units	Description
Relative Humidity	RH	Percentage (%)	Saturation vapor pressure to real water vapor ratio
Dew point temperature	Tdew	Degree Celsius	The temperature at which the air can precisely hold the amount of moisture present is known as the dew point.
Maximum Temperature	Tmax	Degree Celsius	The greatest temperature measured in a certain time period
Minimum Temperature	Tmin	Degree Celsius	The lowest temperature recorded during a specified period of time
Wind Speed	Wspeed	m/s	The speed of wind
Convective available energy	CAPE	J/kg	Estimate of the occurrence of convective rainfall situations
Sunshine	Sunshine	Hour	Hours of shine in a day
Sea surface Temperature	SST	Degree Celsius	The temperature of the water near the surface of the ocean
Rainfall	Rainfall	Millimeter	The amount of water that precipitates in liquid form over a given region and time period; often measured in millimeters or inches

129 **2.2. Models and Technique**

130 **2.2.1. Regression Tree (RT) Model**

131 Decision tree algorithm is used for both classification and regression. The purpose of regression
 132 trees is to predict continuous values, and the sum of squared differences between the predicted and
 133 actual values is used to determine how accurate the predictions are. The RT model consistently
 134 conducts binary partitions for each parameter of the dataset at each level until the prescribed
 135 maximum depth is reached (Liang et al., 2022; Rokach & Maimon, 2005). In this current study,
 136 the problem is a regression problem, and thus a regression tree is used for the study since our
 137 target variable (rainfall) is continuous.

138 **2.2.2. Light Gradient Boosting (LGB) Model**

139 By creating an exclusive feature binding (EFB) operator and gradient-based one-side sampling
 140 (GOSS) to increase efficiency, LGB was further improved to address the computational cost issue.

141 To be more precise, EFB can simplify the feature space by binding the mutually exclusive features,
 142 whereas GOSS down-samples the sample instances and arbitrarily eliminates those with tiny
 143 gradients according to (Tang et al., 2021).

144 LGBM algorithm is based on decision trees therefore the formulation of the model is as follows
 145 (Sibindi et al., 2023). Given a training data set $S = \{(x_i, y_i); i = 1, 2, \dots, n; x_i \in R^m, y_i \in R\}$
 146 where n is the sample with m features. To find the estimation, the decision trees predictions are
 147 combined as follows;

$$148 \quad \hat{y}_i^{LG} = \sum_{p=1}^P f_p(x_i), \quad (4)$$

149 Where the number of trees is p with f_p as the trees. The goal is to minimize the objective function
 150 below to obtain f_p .

$$151 \quad f_p = \arg \min_{f_p} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{LG(p)}) + \Omega(f_p). \quad (5)$$

152 The loss function is L and the regularization parameter Ω which is given by

$$153 \quad \Omega(f_p) = \alpha T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^T w_j^2, \quad (6)$$

154 where α and λ are the penalty parameters for T leaves and weight of leaves w . Taking L as a loss
 155 function which is a squared error, then

$$156 \quad \begin{aligned} L(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{LG(p-1)} + f_p(x)) &= (y_i - \hat{y}_i^{LG(p-1)} - f_p(x))^2 \\ &= (r - f_p(x))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

157 the residual r is fitted to obtain f_p . The function for minimizing the objective function at iteration
 158 p is defined using a quadratic approximation as

$$159 \quad \begin{aligned} f_p &\simeq \arg \min_{f_p} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[g_i f_p(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_p^2(x_i) \right] + \Omega(f_p), \\ g_i &= \partial_{j \omega_{(p-1)}} L(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{LG(p-1)}), \\ h_i &= \partial_{j \leftarrow C_{(p-1)}}^2 L(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{LG(p-1)}). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

160 Through minimizing the objective function, a new tree f_p is obtained. Each node with the biggest
 161 information gain is divided by the decision tree. The variance gains for a node that separates feature
 162 j at point s is given by

163
$$Z_{j|O}(s) = \frac{1}{n_O} \left\{ \frac{\left(\sum_{\{x_i \in O: x_{ij} \leq s\}} g_i \right)^2}{n_{l|O}^j(s)} + \frac{\left(\sum_{\{x_i \in O: x_{ij} > s\}} g_i \right)^2}{n_{r|O}^j(s)} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

164 O is samples on the decision tree fixed node. $n_O = \sum I[x_i \in O]$,
 165 $n_{l|O}^j(s) = \sum I[x_i \in O: x_{ij} \leq s]$ and $n_{r|O}^j(s) = \sum I[x_i \in O: x_{ij} > s]$. The decision tree selects $s_j^* =$
 166 $\arg \max_s Z_j(s)$ for each feature j and computes the highest gain $Z_j(s_j^*)$. The data will be split into
 167 the right and left nodes according to feature j^* at point s_{j^*} . All samples are scanned to find the
 168 optimal splitting point in order to calculate the information gain.

169 **2.2.3. European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast** 170 **(ECMWF) Model-Global Model**

171 The global atmospheric reanalysis product known as European Center for Medium-Range Weather
 172 Forecasts (ECMWF) is created by fusing observational data from satellites and ground
 173 observations with a numerical weather prediction model. The data utilized in the present study
 174 comes from the ERA-5 ECMWF reanalysis product (Gleixner et al., 2020) which provide hourly
 175 meteorological conditions back to 1979. This version of ECMWF reanalysis is based on the
 176 Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) and includes a four-dimensional vibrational analysis (4D-
 177 Var). ERA5 data is available in higher spatial as well as temporal resolution. ERA5 data is
 178 available on a 0.25° grid with hourly intervals. The number of observational datasets that serve as
 179 input for the assimilation system was increased and a major difference is the consideration of
 180 satellite estimates of rainfall in ERA5. For this study, an ERA5 reanalysis rainfall dataset
 181 ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$, hourly), spanning January 2017 to December 2022, was downloaded from the
 182 <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-singlelevels?tab=form>), the
 183 and then the hourly precipitation was converted to a daily scale.

184 **2.3. Development of the Models**

185 **A 29-year (1993-2022) daily interval of meteorological data has been used to train and test models.**
 186 **This data is typically divided into two datasets.** No universal guideline exists for the preparation
 187 of training and testing datasets in both spatial and time series **estimations**. It is recommended to
 188 divide the complete dataset into two sub-datasets for training (80%) and testing (20%) (Khosravi
 189 et al., 2018).

190 In this study modeling were performed using a data from January 1993 to December 2016 (80
 191 percent) of data was used as the training dataset for the model building while data from January
 192 2017 to December 2022 (20 percent) served as the testing dataset for the model development. The
 193 experiments consisted of developing models for rainfall **estimation** over Bahir Dar, Ethiopia using
 194 two different approaches regression tree and light gradient boosting machine learning techniques.
 195 The database was then divided into training and testing subsets.

196 **2.4. Model Hyperparameter Adjustment**

197 Hyperparameters are a set of parameters in machine learning algorithms that need to be adjusted
 198 specifically for a given learning problem because they cannot be predicted from data. The ideal
 199 values of hyperparameters might vary depending on the data and the problem; they are often found
 200 through testing different combinations and evaluating each model's performance. This is a

parameter optimization to select the most suitable set of parameters (Wu et al., 2019) using a trial-and-error process until the best **estimation** score is obtained. The model performance largely depends on the optimization of hyperparameters (Diez-Sierra & Del Jesus, 2020). The study by (Ridwan et al., 2021) found that without tuning, the model (boosting and decision tree regression) performed poorly, but when tuned, the accuracy of the model was noticeably increased. The optimization processes in this study demonstrate that the models tend to gain the minimizing errors, and the relationship between hyperparameters and model accuracy is not linear for all the ML models. Careful consideration is required to tune the hyperparameters. Enlarging the hyperparameters may not improve the ML accuracy. Both accuracy and the computational cost need to be considered in the model development. Maximum tree depth (max depth), number of trees used in ensemble learning (n estimators), fraction of samples to fit individual base learners (subsample), learning rate to minimize the gradient step (learning rate), and maximum number of leaves in each weak learner (num leaves) are the optimal hyperparameters. The range of looked for values and the selected optimum hyperparameters are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2 Optimal hyperparameters of RT and LGB models.

Model	Selected Hyperparameters	Range of search
Regression Tree model	max_depth = 18	[4,5,6,8,12,14,16,18,20]
	min_sample_split = 8	[2,4,5,6,8,10]
	min_sample_split_leaf = 4	[2,4,6]
Light Gradient Boosting model	num_leaves = 160	num-leaves= 100 to 180
	learning-rate = 0.0988	Learning rate = 0.03 to 0.1
	max-depth = 48	max_depth= 18 to 54
	n-estimators = 160	n-estimators = 120 to 200

A GridsearchCV method was implemented to optimize the hyperparameters, identifying the combination that yielded the most accurate results. GridSearchCV is a machine learning technique that uses a methodical search process to determine the best hyperparameters for a given algorithm. It helps identify the hyperparameter sweet spot of a model for optimal performance. Because GridSearchCV employs cross-validation to evaluate model performance after attempting every possible set of hyperparameters, it is incredibly effective (Kartini et al., 2021). Cross-validation can be used to evaluate models on several subsets of the training data in order to prevent overfitting. More parameters were adjusted using the Python GridSearchCV software, and the output was utilized to train the models and produce precise predictions.

2.5. Model Evaluation Methods

Four statistical indicators: mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) were selected to evaluate the robustness of the models. These model effectiveness parameters are utilized to determine performance of models (Abebe & Endalieu, 2023).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_t - \hat{x}_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_t - \bar{x})^2} \quad (10)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_t - \hat{x}_t)^2} \quad (11)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_t - \hat{x}_t| \quad (12)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_t - \hat{x}_t)^2 \quad (13)$$

where x_t is the observed/measured value; \hat{x}_i is the predicted value \bar{x} is the averaged value at time step t.

234

235

Figure 2: Methodology used in this study.

236

3. Results and Discussion

237

3.1. The Correlation of Rainfall and Input Parameters

238

239

240

This section starts by indicating the correlation of input data from 1993 to 2016 that will be used for model development. **The model is intended to be fed with as much data as possible to facilitate the identification and learning of meaningful patterns.** Because one of the most essential phases in

241 developing a predictive model is choosing the input data, which has a big impact on model
242 performance (Ghorbani et al., 2016). The data obtained may contain many attributes or variables,
243 which may or may not be related to the dependent variable. Therefore, for the most accurate
244 analysis of dependent variables, only attributes related to dependent variables should be selected
245 as input models. This study used metrological data for the rainfall **estimation** based on Pearson's
246 correlation. The correlation matrix between the input and output data can be used to confirm these
247 qualities. Finding the features that are most associated with the target variable is simple with a
248 heatmap. To describe the metrological variables that correlate with rainfall and are relevant for
249 rainfall **estimation**, rectangular correlation heat map was used (Salaeh et al., 2022), which shows
250 the Pearson correlation analyzed on the variables presented.

251 The correlation values of all the features are shown in figure 3 and it reveals that, rainfall has
252 strong positive correlation with following parameters: Tdew (94%), Tmin (91%), Wspeed (91%),
253 Tmax (85%), RH (82%); weak positive correlation with CAPE (1.3%) and negative correlation
254 with: SST (2.3%) and sunshine (1.5%). So great importance has been given to dew point due to
255 the fact that it is seen as the measure of the state of the atmosphere in as much that it tells how
256 much water vapor is present in the air condenses into water droplets. The reason of the positive
257 correlation between the wind and rain is that the winds carry an amount of moisture in it which
258 can highly affect the amount of precipitation in an area. Faster winds and precipitation are
259 strongly correlated in nature where faster winds cause rain, showing major significance on daily
260 rainfall variability. RH is the main factor in cloud formation, resulting in rainfall. RH is a key
261 variable for cloud and rainfall (Ackerman et al., 2004). It has also been reported that rainfall is a
262 strongly increasing with RH in different regions of the world (Hardwick Jones et al., 2010;
263 Rushley et al., 2018). **It is found that RH and its derivative variables are among the correlated**
264 **variables**. A significant positive relationship exists between daily minimum temperature and
265 rainfall, whereas a less significant relationship is observed between maximum temperature and
266 rainfall. It is assumed that there is a correlation between rainfall and temperature changes over
267 months. According the study (Cong & Brady, 2012) ,temperature and rainfall were positively
268 correlated during January and May but they negatively correlated in July. Moreover, little is
269 known about the correlation between these types of three variables (minimum temperature,
270 maximum temperature and rainfall) in Ethiopia, particularly in this study area. Therefore, the
271 present study shows the existence of their correlation. Convective available potential energy
272 (CAPE) weakly positive correlate with rainfall which is a crucial indicator of the meteorological
273 conditions needed for convective precipitation events to occur (Seeley & Romps, 2015). It's
274 identified to be among the important correlated variables. This is consistent with previous studies
275 showing that CAPE is an important indicator of extreme precipitation in the eastern US (Gizaw
276 et al., 2021; Lepore et al., 2015). For large-scale climate indices, correlations between rainfall
277 and SST were negatively weak ($r = -0.015$). Positive SST results in reduced rainfall or drought
278 (El Niño). In contrast, negative SST results in high rainfall (La Niña),(Kirtphaiboon et al., 2014).
279 Another weakly correlated variable, sunshine duration is an important indicator of the amount of
280 solar radiation received in a region is $r = -0.23$ with rainfall.

281 **3.2. Relative Feature Importance for Rainfall Estimation**

282 The variable selection or feature/attribute selection in machine learning, identifying and selecting
 283 a subset of relevant features from large set of variables, is crucial step to improve the model's
 284 performance. Feature importance analysis is a useful procedure in the machine learning
 285 community, as it can guide model development by focusing on important variables (Zhou et al.,
 286 2021). **In this work, the Random Forest (RF) technique was employed to determine the importance**
 287 **of each feature for rainfall estimation and to identify the most effective features.** The random forest
 288 model was built and trained daily data, and the significance of the variables was determined. The
 289 use of the random forest is to assess the impact of modifying the variables in a particular model's
 290 capacity of estimation and to quantify the relative importance of the variables in that model.

291
 292 Figure 3: Correlation heat map of features with rainfall.

293 Figure 4 depicts the importance of the input variables as predictors of rainfall by using random
 294 forest model. Among all features, RH ranks first was determined to be most significant parameter,
 295 followed by Tdew, Tmax, CAPE, Tmin, WS, sunshine, and SST with mean importance score of
 296 0.4129, 0.2234, 0.0824, 0.0721, 0.0668, 0.0600, 0.0575, and 0.0245, respectively. It confirms the
 297 findings reported by previous studies by (Zhou et al., 2021) which found that RH ranks first, mean
 298 pressure and sunshine duration rank second and third, and minimum temperature ranks fourth.

299

300 Figure 4: Relative importance of feature variables for rainfall estimation

301 **3.3. Performance of Models for Temporal Rainfall Variation**

302 This section examines observed rainfall variability with test data over the region and shows how
 303 our developed models are reliable to show the temporal variability of rainfall. Moreover, the
 304 section also consists of intercomparison LGB, RT and ECMWF model.

305 **3.4. Estimating Daily Rainfall**

306 Figure 5 shows the performance of tree-based machine learning and global model to predict daily
 307 rainfall variation. To predict daily rainfall LGB, RT and the global model called ECMWF are
 308 utilized in order to predict and select a feasible model for daily rainfall **estimation** over the region.
 309 These models are compared to each other based on their performance, feasibility, and accuracy in
 310 examining observed rainfall. Their accuracy was examined using statistical model evaluation
 311 metrics. The performance of the LGB, RT, ECMWF model was expressed with four main
 312 statistical indicators: R^2 , RMSE, MSE, and MAE, which were significantly considered.

313

314 Figure 5: Scatter plot of estimated versus measured daily rainfall values testing phase (marked black dot) with the
 315 linear fit (blue line) (a) using LGB model (b) using RT model and (c) using ECMWF model.

316 The plots of figure 5 in the panels are LGB, RT, and ECMWF from left to right in order. The R^2
 317 score for LGB, RT, and ECMWF models, are 0.991, 0.874, and 0.778, respectively. The scatter
 318 plots depict that the predicting ability of the rainfall models agrees with observed values. However,
 319 their degrees of agreement are different. The LGBM model agrees the most. The RT model agrees
 320 better than that of the ECMWF model but less than LGBM. The LGB model is strong candidate
 321 predict rainfall in this temporal rainfall variation.

322 Figure 6 : Histogram of error distribution of daily rainfall for testing phase using (a) LGB model, (b) using RT
 323 model and bottom panel (c) using ECMWF model.

324 To investigate whether there are systematic deviations of model's estimation from the observed
 325 daily rainfall variation figure 6 presents the variance distribution of daily deviation probability for
 326 LGB, RT and ECMWF models left to right in order. The statistical error metrics of LGB, RT and
 327 ECMWF models with RMSE in mm (1.411, 7.31, and 7.892). The LGB model had the lowest
 328 RMSE value (1.411mm) making it the most accurate in predicting daily rainfall variation. In
 329 contrast, ECMWF model had the highest RMSE (7.892 mm). The LGB model returned the
 330 smallest value (MAE = 0.899 mm) indicating that the deviation between the predicted and
 331 measured values was also the smallest. The ECMWF model's MAE was the highest (MAE =

332 4.306mm) indicating that it had the greatest **estimation** bias. The findings also revealed that the
 333 MSE in mm of the LGB, RT and ECMWF 1.992, 53.44, 62.28, respectively. As aforementioned
 334 numerical values, the MSE of LGBM (1.992 mm) is smaller than that of both the RT (53.44mm)
 335 and ECMWF models (62.28), which implies that LGB performs better than other models. The
 336 ECMWF model shows relatively poor performance. The LGB strong, RT models had relatively
 337 good predictive ability, whereas the ECMWF performed badly, according to the results of the daily
 338 data **estimations**. For further verification of the performance of each model, their daily statistical
 339 evaluation metrics values are displayed in Table 3.

340 Table 3: Daily statistical values of each model

	LGBM	RT	ECMWF
R ²	0.9910	0.874	0.778
MSE (mm)	1.992	53.44	62.28
RMSE (mm)	1.411	7.31	7.892
MAE (mm)	0.899	4.27	4.306

341

342 **3.5. Comparison of Models Performance for Daily – Trend of Rainfall** 343 **Variation**

344 **In this section, the daily trend variation of rainfall was examined and compared using results**
 345 **obtained from the LGB, RT, and ECMWF.** The trend analysis is focused on understanding the
 346 differences between observed and model results. In Figure 7, the observed and predicted daily
 347 rainfall values for testing data are plotted to illustrate the capability of the model in capturing the
 348 trends of day-to-day time series variability. As can be seen, the modeled rainfall values closely
 349 follow the observed, which proves that the developed model is consistent with the observed rainfall
 350 pattern. A close inspection of these figures shows that the LGB model with optimal parameters
 351 predicts rainfall very similar to the observed values, followed by RT and ECMWF. ECMWF has
 352 poor capability. It is seen from the figures that the predicted rainfall follows a typical daily
 353 variability for the study region. The machine learning models (green and purple lines in the time
 354 series) closely follow the observed rainfall (black line in the time series), suggesting improvements
 355 in RMSE, MAE, MSE, and R² over ECMWF.

356

357 Figure 7: Time series plot of daily rainfall variation using LGB, RT and ECMWF models

358 However, once larger rainfall accumulation amounts are attained, the model's ensemble members'
 359 disagreement could escalate, making it less accurate in predicting extreme precipitation. This
 360 result is similar to that of the study by (Nguyen et al., 2018; Olaniyan et al., 2018). These results
 361 indicate that LGBM and RT models generally have a better capability of predicting rainfall for
 362 less rainy seasons rather than that for wet seasons. The result is also supported by (Zhou et al.,
 363 2021). The ECMWF model has relatively less skill to capture the variation of rainfall due to its
 364 models cover a wider area, and a longer time span, they're generally run at a lower resolution, both
 365 spatially (fewer forecast points per given area) and temporally (fewer time points get a forecast).
 366 Generally, LGB and RT models have better agreement with observed rainfall than ECMF models.

367 **3.6. Comparison of Model Performance for Monthly Rainfall Variation**

368 This section aims to show the feasibility of using LGB, RT tree-based models and the ECMWF
 369 global model for monthly rainfall variation. The monthly predicted and measured values of rainfall
 370 variation for models are shown in a scatter plot in figure 8. As shown in figure; monthly rainfall
 371 model simulated using LGB, RT and ECMWF models have R^2 values of 0.996, 0.940, and 0.925,
 372 respectively. According to given result LGB model is strong candidate than other two models. The
 373 best result was achieved by the LGB with $R^2 = 0.996$, followed by RT with $R^2 = 0.940$. But
 374 ECMWF have the least accurate predictions of monthly rainfall with R^2 value of 0.925 compared
 375 to that of both LGB and RT models.

376

377 Figure 8: Scatter plot of **estimated** versus measured monthly rainfall values testing phase (marked black dot) with
 378 the linear fit (blue line) (a) using LGB model (b) using RT model and (c) using ECMWF model.

379

380 Figure 9: Histogram of error distribution of monthly rainfall for testing phase using (a) LGB model, (b) using RT
 381 model and bottom panel (c) using ECMWF model.

382 Figure 9 shows the statistical model evaluation metrics of the LGB model with RMSE = 0.383mm,
 383 MAE = 0.302mm, and MSE = 0.146mm; the RT model with RMSE = 1.541mm, MAE = 0.838mm,
 384 and MSE = 2.375mm; and the ECMWF model with RMSE = 1.727mm, MAE = 1.166mm, and
 385 MSE = 2.375mm. As per the aforementioned numerical values, the RMSE, MAE, and MSE of the
 386 LGBM model are smaller than those of both the RT and ECMWF models, which implies that LGB
 387 performs better than other models. This means the **estimating** ability of the LGB model is better
 388 than that of other models. RT second, and ECMWF least because of RMSE, MAE, and MSE of
 389 ECMWF > RMSE, MAE, and MSE of RT > RMSE, MAE, and MSE of LGB.

390 At the monthly scale, most of the R^2 values for each model are larger. This shows the **estimating**
 391 ability of the LGB model has better agreement with measured or observed values than the daily
 392 time scale, which is shown by the good fit between predicted and observed rainfall. The amount
 393 of rainfall variation estimated by the tree-based machine learning model captures the trend of the
 394 observed monthly variation in rainfall rate. Our model estimation almost agrees with observed

395 rainfall variation, and ECMWF also agrees well with observed rainfall variation in this temporal
396 variation case.

397 The optimal model for rainfall modeling using all the performance criteria is found to be LGB.
398 These models have one of the lowest RMSE, MAE, and MSE, and the highest R^2 compared to that
399 of RT, ECMWF. ECMWF has relatively high RMSE, MAE, MSE and low R^2 values. The LGB
400 has been found to be the most generalizing and accurate in rainfall modeling.

401 Our study describes the monthly time scale modeling's have better agreements with the observed
402 effects than daily time scale modeling's, which is shown by the good fits between modeled and
403 observed plots. This result is also confirmed by the study (Nguyen et al., 2018).

404 Table 4 Statistical criteria of three models for monthly rainfall scale

	Monthly Rainfall Variation		
	LGB	RT	ECMWF
R^2	0.996	0.940	0.925
RMSE (mm)	0.383	1.541	1.727
MSE (mm)	0.146	2.375	2.982
MAE (mm)	0.302	0.838	1.166

405 **3.7. Comparison of Models Performance for Monthly – Trend of Rainfall** 406 **Variation**

407 This section shows the average monthly rainfall pattern/trend and the feasibility of our model to
408 capture the monthly trends of rainfall over the Bahir Dar sector. While the highest average rainfall
409 at Bahir Dar is in July, rainfall increases gradually from May at 4.5 mm and reaches its maximum
410 in July at 18.5 mm. This has been the general rainfall pattern in Bahir Dar Station, and the
411 maximum rainfall occurs once a year. The rainfall pattern at can be referred to as a uni-modal
412 rainfall distribution (Elvis et al., 2015). The results from the model and observed data confirm that
413 stations with a uni-modal rainfall distribution have rainfall periods ranging from May to
414 September, with July and August recording the highest amount of rainfall.

415

416 Figure 10: Trend of average monthly rainfall of the year 2017 to 2022 over Bahir Dar using models.

417 As shown in figure 10, the LGB model shows a similar rainfall pattern to that of the observed data
 418 but grossly underestimates the amount of rainfall in all the months except for June, September,
 419 and October. Similarly, the RT model shows a similar rainfall pattern to that of the observed data
 420 but grossly underestimates the amount of rainfall in all the months except for May, June, and
 421 October. As suggested by (Afiesimama et al., 2006) the differences (overestimation and
 422 underestimation) in the model results and observed may be due to the coarse nature of the
 423 horizontal grid of the model to accurately simulate the mesoscale systems and nature of training
 424 data.

425 It's the justified that LGB performed best for June, July, August, and September. RT for well
 426 performs with rainy months October, December June and May rainfalls. Both LGB and RT models
 427 is good candidate for rainy month rainfall prediction. ECMWF underestimates the amount of
 428 rainfall in all the months. The ECMWF model was insignificant because it grossly underestimated
 429 the amount of rainfall in all the months. The ECMWF reanalysis model generally had the largest
 430 discrepancies when compared with the other models. This is due to the fact that several algorithms
 431 and models based on multiple wavelengths have been developed to derive rainfall estimates.
 432 Nevertheless, it is essential to note that rainfall estimates derived from the ECMWF are indirect
 433 and are inevitably accompanied by a large degree of variability. For instance, many previous
 434 studies have indicated that reanalysis-based models generally have difficulty in representing
 435 rainfall in areas with complex topography in which rainfall is controlled by the orography and
 436 characterized by high spatiotemporal variability (Sun et al., 2018).

437 Overall, the outcome of this study suggests that the LGBM and RT models have the potential to
 438 be suitable for the study of rainfall variability and trend studies over Bahir Dar. The ability of
 439 this model to accurately predict rainfall variability from the observed data can play a vital role
 440 even in water resources management Bahir Dar since the observed data are generally sparse and
 441 riddled with gaps.

442

443 **4. Conclusion**

444 This study builds two tree-based machine learning) models (i. e., Regression Tree (RT) and Light
445 Gradient Boosting Machine (LGB)) for **estimation** of rainfall, based on a local input metrological
446 parameters (relative humidity, dew point temperature, minimum temperature, maximum
447 temperature, wind speed, convective available potential energy, and sunshine) as well as large-
448 scale climate variable such as sea surface temperature. Firstly, the given data from NMI is
449 preprocessed and feed into models with split into a training and a testing set. Then, through
450 GrideserchCV, the machine learning models are tuned to achieve a high accuracy. Tree based
451 machine learning models have achieved high accuracy in the testing set ($R^2 > 0.874$), which largely
452 outperforms the broadly used global model, ECMWF ($R^2 = 0.778$) for daily rainfall variation.
453 Similarly for monthly variation LGB and RT achieve high accuracy in the testing set ($R^2 > 0.940$),
454 outperforms the broadly used global model, ECMWF ($R^2 = 0.925$). Compared with RT and
455 ECMWF, LGBM can achieve higher accuracy in significantly for both temporal rainfall variations:
456 the R^2 of LGB, RT and ECMWF are 0.991, 0.874, and 0.778 respectively, for daily while their
457 monthly is also 0.996, 0.940, and 0.925 respectively. Strong correlation between rainfall and the
458 dew point temperature (Tdew), minimum temperature (Tmin), wind speed (Wspeed), relative
459 humidity (RH), and maximum temperature (Tmax) using heat map method. Their range of
460 correlation is within ($r = 0.82$ to 0.94). On the other hand, convective available potential energy
461 (CAPE) weakly positive and sea surface temperature (SST) and sunshine (sunshine) weak negative
462 the relevant atmospheric features that correlate with rainfall. Their range of correlation is also
463 within the range of ($r = -0.015$ to 0.013). Although using RF model for features important analysis,
464 RF model produces the parameters relative humidity (RH), dew point temperature (Tdew) features
465 important analysis with RF score of 0.4129, 0.2234 respectively. This feature important analysis
466 is consistent with common knowledge about factors that influence rainfall, which validates the
467 reasonability of proposed RF model for feature important analysis. For future work, the use of
468 additional datasets and exploring other places and locations throughout the Ethiopia would be a
469 good option for building a strong model.

470 **Data Availability**

471 The authors used the data from Ethiopian meteorological institute, Bahir Dar sector and
472 Copernicus' Climate Data Store with link
473 <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=form>

474 **Declaration of interests**

475 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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